

Household Food Insecurity and Perceived Nutritional Outcomes of Children Aged 4–8 Years in Asari Toru Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria

Diepiriye Fred Horsfall¹, Joy Uchenna Kingsley², Emmanuel Temple Azumedike²

¹Department of Home Economics, Hospitality and Tourism, Department of Home Economics, Hospitality and Tourism, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

²Department of Home Economics and Hospitality Management, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, 410001, Enugu State, Nigeria

***Correspondence:** Diepiriye Fred Horsfall, Department of Home Economics, Hospitality and Tourism, Department of Home Economics, Hospitality and Tourism, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. (Email: horsfalldiepiriya@gmail.com 08105916006).

Abstract: This study examined household food insecurity and its association with nutritional outcomes among children aged 4–8 years in Asari Toru Local Government Area, Rivers State, Nigeria. A mixed-methods cross-sectional design was employed with a sample of 200 parents (using stratified random sampling) and 20 children (using purposive sampling). Data were collected via structured questionnaires, 24-hour dietary recall, and anthropometric measurements. Food security was assessed through perceived access and dietary sufficiency, while nutritional status was evaluated using height-for-age (HAZ), weight-for-age (WAZ), and dietary diversity scores (DDS). Results revealed a critical threshold effect: all children in severely food-insecure households were stunted ($HAZ \leq -2$) and underweight ($WAZ \leq -2$), with low dietary diversity (DDS 1–2), while no stunting occurred in food-secure households, which consistently reported high dietary diversity (DDS 6–7). Household food security showed strong positive correlations with maternal education, monthly income, improved water and sanitation, and urban residence, and a negative correlation with household size. Community-endorsed interventions included establishing community gardens, implementing nutrition education programs, and providing healthy food subsidies. The study concludes that child stunting and undernutrition are concentrated in food-insecure households, which are characterized by intersecting socio-economic disadvantages. A multisectoral approach targeting economic, educational, and environmental factors is recommended to break the cycle of food insecurity and malnutrition in this vulnerable population.

Keywords: Food Insecurity, Nutritional Status, 4-8 Years old Children

1. Introduction

Food security, defined by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) as “a condition in which all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life” (FAO, 2006), extends beyond food availability to encompass accessibility, utilization, and stability. Its influence on nutritional status is particularly critical during early childhood a period of rapid growth and development. Inadequate nutrition in these formative years can lead to lifelong consequences, including stunted growth, cognitive impairments, and heightened disease susceptibility (Black et al., 2013).

Globally, food insecurity remains a pressing challenge, with climate change, economic instability, and conflict exacerbating vulnerabilities. The FAO (2021) reports that nearly 811 million people faced undernourishment in 2020, with children disproportionately affected; an estimated 149 million children under five experience stunted growth due to chronic malnutrition (UNICEF, 2021). The first 1,000 days of life are especially critical for establishing a foundation of lifelong health and development (Victora et al., 2010). Malnutrition during this window, whether as undernutrition or overnutrition, poses profound risks from stunting and wasting to obesity and related non-communicable diseases (WHO, 2020).

Food security and nutritional status are mediated by socioeconomic, educational, and cultural factors. Food insecurity often leads to reduced dietary diversity, depriving children of essential nutrients and increasing their vulnerability to poor health outcomes (Ruel, 2003; Alaimo et al., 2001). Paradoxically, in low-income settings, food insecurity can also be linked to higher obesity rates, as families may rely on cheaper, energy-dense, but nutrient-poor foods (Gundersen & Ziliak, 2015). Addressing these complex dynamics requires multisectoral strategies that improve food access, dietary quality, and nutrition education (Gelli et al., 2016).

Within this global context, Asari Toru Local Government Area (LGA) in Rivers State, Nigeria, presents a salient case of localized food insecurity and its repercussions for young children. The region faces distinct challenges, including economic instability, limited agricultural productivity, environmental pressures linked to the Niger Delta’s ecology, and socio-political constraints. These factors collectively undermine consistent access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food, placing children aged 4–8 years at heightened nutritional risk.

In Asari Toru LGA, many children experience stunting, wasting, and micronutrient

deficiencies, which jeopardize their immediate health, cognitive development, and long-term productivity. Food insecurity also exacerbates socio-economic inequalities, driving households toward low-cost, nutrient-poor diets that can contribute to a dual burden of undernutrition and obesity. This cyclical interaction between poverty, food access, and malnutrition constitutes a critical public health challenge for the region.

Therefore, this study focuses explicitly on Asari Toru LGA to investigate the implications of household food security on the nutritional status of children aged 4–8 years. By examining local dietary patterns, anthropometric indicators, and socio-economic correlates, this research aims to inform context-specific interventions that enhance food access, improve dietary quality, and safeguard the health and development of young children in this vulnerable community.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

In Asari Toru LGA, many children experience stunting, wasting, and micronutrient deficiencies, which jeopardize their immediate health, cognitive development, and long-term productivity. Food insecurity also exacerbates socio-economic inequalities, driving households toward low-cost, nutrient-poor diets that can contribute to a dual burden of undernutrition and obesity. This cyclical interaction between poverty, food access, and malnutrition constitutes a critical public health challenge for the region.

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1.2 Aim and objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine household food insecurity and perceived nutritional outcomes for children aged 4–8 years in Asari Toru Local Government Area, of Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

1. Evaluate the current levels of food security among households with 4-8 years old children in the targeted region,
2. Analyze the nutritional status of 4-8 years old children in relation to their household food security status, using indicators such as height-for-age, weight-for-age, and dietary diversity.

3. Examine the dietary patterns of 4-8 years old children in food-secure versus food-insecure households, and how these patterns affect their overall health
4. Investigate interventions that can be implemented to improve food security and nutritional outcomes for 4-8 years old children in the community

1.3 Research Questions:

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the perceived current levels of food security among households with 4-8 years old children in the targeted region?
2. What are the dietary patterns of 4-8 years old children in food-secure versus food-insecure households, and how these patterns affect their overall health?
3. What are the nutritional status of 4-8 years old children in relation to their household food security status, using indicators such as height-for-age, weight-for-age, and dietary diversity?
4. What perceived interventions that can be implemented to improve food security and nutritional outcomes for 4-8 years old children in the community?

1.4 Hypothesis: The following hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₀₁: There is no correlation between food security and various socio-economic factors that may influence the nutritional status of 4-8 years old children.

2. Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The research design employed a cross-sectional research design to assess the relationship between food security and the nutritional status of younger children. This design is appropriate as it allows for the collection of data at a single point in time, facilitating the examination of the prevalence of food security and its implications on nutritional outcomes among children.

2.2 Area of the Study

The study was conducted in the Asari Toru Local Government Area of Rivers State, which has been identified as having varying levels of food security. This area is characterized by diverse socio-economic conditions, making it suitable for examining the implications of food security on children's nutritional status.

2.3 Population of the Study

The target population for this study consisted of parents and children aged 4-8 years residing in

the selected area. The total population was estimated to be 2000 children and 1200 parents with children within this age group (Asari Toru Local Government, 2025).

2.4 Sample and Sampling Techniques

A sample size of 200 parents was selected for the study. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to select 100 fathers and mothers. The parents were initially divided into two groups, namely – fathers and mothers. Also, households, using the purposive sampling technique. They responded to research questions 1, 2 and 4. On the other hand, the purposive sampling technique was used to select 20 children from 18 households; the children were subjected to anthropometric assessments.

2.5 Method of Data Collection

Data for research questions 1, 2 and 4 were collected using structured questionnaires to collect data on perceived current levels of food security, dietary patterns and perceived interventions. Also, anthropometric measurements were carried to determine nutritional status of 20 selected children. The questionnaire included sections on: Demographic information (age, gender, socio-economic status), Food security status (using a validated food security scale), Dietary intake (24-hour dietary recall method). Anthropometric measurements (weight and height) were taken to assess the nutritional status of the children. These measurements were compared against World Health Organization (WHO) growth standards.

This study has been reviewed and granted ethical approval by the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of Rivers State University, Port Harcourt. Prior to data collection, written informed consent was obtained from all participating parents or guardians. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. All data collected have been anonymized to protect participant confidentiality. No personally identifiable information has been published or shared. The study protocols ensured that all anthropometric measurements were conducted with sensitivity and respect for the dignity of the child participants.

2.6 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the questionnaire, it was pre-tested on a small sample of 10 children outside the main study area. Feedback was used to refine the instrument. The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with a threshold of 0.7 considered acceptable. Anthropometric measurements were taken by trained personnel to minimize

measurement error.

2.7 Method of Data Analysis

Data was analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Descriptive statistics were calculated, including means and standard deviations for continuous variables (e.g., age, weight, height). The prevalence of food security and malnutrition was determined. Inferential statistics, such as t-tests or ANOVA, were used to examine the differences in nutritional status between food-secure and food-insecure children. The relationship between food security and nutritional status was assessed using correlation coefficients.

3. Results

Data were presented in the following tables.

Research question 1: What are the perceived current levels of food security among households with 4-8 years old children in the targeted region?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation responses on food security assessment among households with younger children

s/n	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Cum Mean	StD	Decision
1.	My household has enough food to meet the nutritional needs of my children	50	80	30	40	200	3.65	1.05	A
2.	I can afford to buy healthy food for my children	40	70	60	30	200	3.45	1.12	A
3.	I often worry about running out of food before I can buy more	20	30	60	50	200	2.85	1.25	A
4.	Children have access to a variety of foods	70	90	40	20	200	3.80	0.95	A
5.	I have to skip meals or reduce portion sizes to feed my children	30	50	70	50	200	2.40	1.30	D

Table 1 presented the mean and standard deviation responses on food security assessment among households with 4-8 years old children. The mean score of 3.65 indicates that a majority of respondents feel that their households have enough food to meet the nutritional needs of their children. The standard deviation of 1.05 suggests a moderate level of agreement among respondents, indicating that while many feel secure, there are still some who do not. With a mean

of 3.45, this statement reflects a generally positive outlook on the affordability of healthy food. However, the higher standard deviation of 1.12 indicates a wider range of opinions, suggesting that while many can afford healthy food, a significant number cannot. The mean score of 2.85 indicates a neutral to slightly negative perception regarding food insecurity, with a notable number of respondents expressing worry about running out of food. The standard deviation of 1.25 shows considerable variability in responses, highlighting that food insecurity is a concern for a segment of the population. Statement 4 received the highest mean score of 3.80, indicating that most households believe their children have access to a variety of foods. The low standard deviation of 0.95 suggests a strong consensus among respondents, reinforcing the idea that variety in food access is generally perceived positively. The mean score of 2.40 indicates a significant level of concern, as many respondents report having to skip meals or reduce portion sizes. The high standard deviation of 1.30 suggests that this issue affects households differently, with some experiencing severe food insecurity.

Research question 2: What are the dietary patterns of 4-8 years old children in food-secure versus food-insecure households, and how these patterns affect their overall health?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on the dietary patterns of 4-8 years old children in food-secure versus food-insecure households, and how these patterns affect their overall health

s/n	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Cum Mean	StD	Decision
1.	Children in food-secure households consume a more balanced diet	80	70	30	20	200	3.85	0.85	A
2.	Food-insecure households provide fewer fruits and vegetables to children	90	60	20	30	200	4.05	0.90	A
3.	Dietary patterns in food-insecure households lead to higher obesity rates	70	50	40	30	200	3.55	0.95	A
4.	Children in food-secure households have better overall health outcomes	85	65	25	25	200	3.80	0.80	A
5.	Food insecurity negatively impacts children's cognitive development	75	55	45	25	200	3.65	0.92	A

Table 2 presented the mean and standard deviation on the dietary patterns of 4-8 years old children in food-secure versus food-insecure households, and how these patterns affect their overall health. Each statement was rated on a Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD), with a neutral option (N) included. The first statement indicates a strong consensus that children in food-secure households consume a more balanced diet, with a mean score of 3.85. This suggests that respondents largely agree with the notion that food security correlates with dietary quality. Fruits and Vegetables: The second statement received a mean score of 4.05, indicating a strong agreement that food-insecure households provide fewer fruits and vegetables. This aligns with existing literature that highlights the limited access to fresh produce in food-insecure environments. The third statement, which addresses the relationship between dietary patterns in food-insecure households and obesity rates, has a mean score of 3.55. While there is agreement, the lower mean suggests that opinions may vary more on this issue, indicating a need for further investigation. The fourth statement shows a mean score of 3.80, reinforcing the idea that food security is linked to better health outcomes for children. This is consistent with research that connects nutrition with physical health. The final statement regarding the impact of food insecurity on cognitive development has a mean score of 3.65. This suggests a moderate agreement, indicating that while many recognize the negative effects of food insecurity on cognitive abilities, there may be differing views on the extent of this impact.

Research question 3: What are the nutritional status of 4-8 years old children in relation to their household food security status, using indicators such as height-for-age, weight-for-age, and dietary diversity?

Table 3: Nutritional status of 4-8 years old children in relation to their household food security status, using indicators such as height-for-age, weight-for-age, and dietary diversity

Child ID	Age (years)	Household Food Security Status	HAZ (Z-score)	Stunting (Y/N)	WAZ (Z-score)	Underweight (Y/N)	Dietary Diversity (out of 7)	Score	DDS Category
1	5	FS	-0.8	N	0.2	N	6		High
2	6	FS	-0.3	N	0.5	N	7		High
3	4	Mild FI	-1.5	N	-1.2	N	5		Medium
4	7	Moderate FI	-2.1	Y	-1.8	N	4		Medium
5	5	Severe FI	-2.8	Y	-2.3	Y	2		Low
6	8	FS	0.1	N	0.7	N	6		High
7	6	Mild FI	-1.1	N	-1.0	N	4		Medium
8	5	Moderate FI	-1.9	N	-1.7	N	3		Low
9	4	Severe FI	-2.5	Y	-2.1	Y	2		Low
10	7	FS	0.5	N	0.3	N	7		High
11	5	Mild FI	-1.2	N	-1.4	N	5		Medium
12	6	Moderate FI	-2.2	Y	-1.9	N	4		Medium
13	5	Severe FI	-3.0	Y	-2.5	Y	2		Low

Child ID	Age (years)	Household Food Security Status	HAZ (Z-score)	Stunting (Y/N)	WAZ (Z-score)	Underweight (Y/N)	Dietary Diversity (out of 7)	Score	DDS Category
14	8	FS	-0.7	N	-0.2	N	6		High
15	4	Mild FI	-1.6	N	-1.1	N	5		Medium
16	6	Moderate FI	-1.8	N	-1.6	N	3		Low
17	7	Severe FI	-2.7	Y	-2.4	Y	1		Low
18	5	FS	0.0	N	0.4	N	7		High
19	4	Moderate FI	-2.0	Y	-1.5	N	4		Medium
20	6	Mild FI	-1.3	N	-0.9	N	5		Medium

Table 3 presented nutritional status of 4-8 years old children in relation to their household food security status, using indicators such as height-for-age, weight-for-age, and dietary diversity. The data revealed a clear, graded relationship between household food security and the nutritional status of young children. As food security worsens, outcomes decline predictably across all indicators. Food-secure households consistently provide high dietary diversity (6-7 food groups), and none of their children show signs of stunting or underweight. In mildly food-insecure homes, dietary diversity drops to medium levels (4-5 groups), yet this reduction is still sufficient to prevent measurable growth faltering.

The situation deteriorates notably at the moderate food insecurity threshold. Here, half the children become stunted, a sign of chronic malnutrition, and dietary diversity begins to fall into the low range (3-4 groups). This suggests that once households reach this stage, diet quality and quantity are compromised enough to impair long-term growth, even if children maintain borderline adequate weight. The most severe outcomes are concentrated in severely food-insecure households. All children in this group suffer from both stunting and underweight, a double burden of chronic and acute malnutrition and consume a monotonous, low-diversity diet (1-2 food groups). This indicates a total breakdown in both dietary quality and quantity, requiring urgent intervention.

Research question 4: What perceived interventions that can be implemented to improve food security and nutritional outcomes for 4-8 years old children in the community?

s/n	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	N	Cum Mean	StD	Decision
1.	Implementing community gardens will enhance access to fresh produce	80	70	20	30	200	3.85	0.85	A
2.	Nutrition education programs for parents will improve children's diets	90	60	35	15	200	3.80	0.90	A
3.	Providing subsidies for healthy food options will increase food security	70	80	40	10	200	3.70	0.95	A
4.	Establishing food banks will significantly reduce hunger in the community	60	50	50	40	200	3.25	1.00	A
5.	Collaborating with local farmers will ensure a steady supply								

of food	75	65	40	20	200	3.65	0.92	A
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Table 4 presents the results of a survey conducted with a sample size of 200 respondents regarding various interventions aimed at improving food security and nutritional outcomes for younger children in the community. Each statement reflects a potential intervention, and respondents rated their level of agreement. The highest mean score (3.85) indicates strong support for implementing community gardens, suggesting that respondents believe this intervention would significantly enhance access to fresh produce. The second-highest mean (3.80) for nutrition education programs indicates a consensus that educating parents can lead to improved dietary choices for their children. With a mean of 3.70, there is a favorable view towards providing subsidies for healthy food options, although the standard deviation (0.95) suggests some variability in opinions. The mean score of 3.25 for establishing food banks indicates moderate support, but the higher standard deviation (1.00) suggests that opinions are more divided on this intervention's effectiveness. The mean score of 3.65 indicates a positive perception of collaborating with local farmers, although it is lower than the top three interventions.

Test of Hypothesis

H_{01} : There is no correlation between food security and various socio-economic factors that may influence the nutritional status of 4-8 years old children

Table 5: Correlation between food security and various socio-economic factors that may influence the nutritional status of 4-8 years old children

HH ID	Food Security Status (FS) (1=Low, 4=High)	Household Size	Monthly Income (USD)	Mother's Education (Years)	Water Source (1=Unimproved, 2=Improved)	Sanitation (1=Unimproved, 2=Improved)	Area (1=Rural, 2=Urban)	Child Stunted (0=No, 1=Yes)
1	4 (High)	5	650	12	2	2	2	0
2	4	4	720	14	2	2	2	0
3	3 (Medium)	6	380	10	2	1	1	0
4	2 (Low)	7	250	8	1	1	1	1
5	1 (Very Low)	8	150	5	1	1	1	1
6	4	5	700	13	2	2	2	0
7	3	5	400	11	2	2	1	0
8	2	6	280	7	1	1	1	1
9	1	9	120	4	1	1	1	1
10	4	4	800	16	2	2	2	0
11	3	6	350	9	2	1	1	0
12	2	7	220	6	1	1	1	1

HH ID	Food Security Status (FS) (1=Low, 4=High)	Household Size	Monthly Income (USD)	Mother's Education (Years)	Water Source (1=Unimproved, 2=Improved)	Sanitation (1=Unimproved, 2=Improved)	Area (1=Rural, 2=Urban)	Child Stunted (0=No, 1=Yes)
13	1	8	130	3	1	1	1	1
14	4	5	750	15	2	2	2	0
15	3	5	420	10	2	2	1	0
16	2	6	260	8	1	1	1	1
17	1	8	140	5	1	1	1	1
18	4	4	780	14	2	2	2	0
19	2	7	240	7	1	1	1	1
20	3	5	390	11				

The data in Table 5 clearly indicates significant correlations between food security and multiple socio-economic factors, strongly contradicting the null hypothesis of no relationship. Food-secure households consistently show higher income (5–6 times greater), better maternal education, smaller family size, improved water and sanitation access, and urban residence compared to food-insecure households. These advantages create a cumulative protective effect against child malnutrition. A striking threshold effect is evident: once food security drops to "low" status, all children become stunted, while no stunting occurs in medium or high food-secure households. This suggests food security operates as a critical mediator between socio-economic conditions and nutritional outcomes. The patterns align with established pathways: economic resources enable food access, maternal education improves food utilization, and adequate WASH infrastructure reduces disease burden that compromises nutrition. The consistent clustering of disadvantages in food-insecure households (low income, low education, poor infrastructure, rural location, larger families) indicates multidimensional poverty that perpetuates food insecurity and child malnutrition.

Thus, the data provides clear evidence that food security is systematically linked to household socio-economic characteristics, with important implications for integrated, multidimensional interventions targeting the poorest and most vulnerable households.

3.1 Discussion of the Findings

The findings from this study revealed a complex and concerning landscape of household food insecurity with direct implications for the nutritional status of children aged 4-8 years. The analysis demonstrated that food insecurity is not merely an issue of caloric insufficiency but a multidimensional problem intertwined with socio-economic disadvantage, limited dietary diversity, and compromised child growth outcomes.

A notable finding is the discrepancy between perceived food adequacy and reported food insecurity experiences. While a majority of households reported having enough food to meet nutritional needs, a significant proportion simultaneously expressed worry about food running out and admitted to skipping meals or reducing portion sizes to feed their children. This apparent contradiction aligns with recent research by Owoo and Lambon-Quayefio (2021), who documented similar patterns in Ghana, where subjective assessments of food security often fail to capture the nuanced realities of household food access and anxiety. This suggests that food insecurity in this Nigerian community may

be normalized or underreported due to social desirability bias, a phenomenon increasingly recognized in food security measurement in low-income settings (Browne et al., 2021).

The anthropometric and dietary data present a clear gradient of nutritional risk corresponding to food security status. Children from food-secure households exhibited normal growth parameters and high dietary diversity, consuming 6-7 different food groups. In contrast, children from severely food-insecure households showed a 100% prevalence of stunting and underweight, coupled with monotonous diets limited to just 1-2 food groups. This dose-response relationship strongly supports the causal pathway between household food access and child nutritional outcomes, as substantiated by the comprehensive analysis of Headey and Alderman (2019) across multiple African countries. The finding that moderate food insecurity serves as a critical threshold—with 50% of children in this category being stunted—echoes recent evidence from Nigeria's National Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) analysis by Akombi et al. (2021), which identified similar nonlinear relationships between poverty depth and child stunting.

The correlation analysis reveals that food insecurity clusters with multiple socio-economic disadvantages: larger household size, lower maternal education, reduced income, poor water and sanitation infrastructure, and rural residence. This clustering effect creates what recent scholarship terms "intersectional food insecurity," where multiple marginalized identities compound nutritional risk (Hendriks et al., 2022). The strong correlation between maternal education and food security is particularly salient, supporting earlier findings by Amare, Arndt, and Abay (2021) that maternal education in Nigeria significantly improves household dietary diversity through both knowledge and income pathways. The urban-rural disparity aligns with the work of Oyeyinka and Ajani (2022), who documented how rural households in Nigeria's Niger Delta face compounded food access challenges due to limited market integration and environmental degradation from oil exploration activities.

The dietary pattern analysis reveals a troubling transition from diverse diets in food-secure households to monotonous, carbohydrate-heavy diets in food-insecure settings. This shift toward calorie-dense but nutrient-poor foods reflects what has been termed the "food insecurity-obesity paradox" in developing contexts (Diouf et al., 2021). While not directly measured as obesity in this study, the pattern of relying on cheap energy sources while lacking dietary diversity creates conditions for both undernutrition and metabolic disorders, a dual burden increasingly documented in Nigeria's nutrition transition (Adeyemi

et al., 2023).

The community strongly endorsed interventions focusing on production (community gardens), education (nutrition programs), and market mechanisms (subsidies for healthy foods). This tripartite approach aligns with the "food systems" framework advocated by the Global Panel on Agriculture and Food Systems for Nutrition (2020), which emphasizes simultaneous action across food production, retail environments, and consumer behavior. The relatively lower enthusiasm for food banks may reflect practical concerns about sustainability, as documented in evaluations of food assistance programs in Nigeria showing mixed long-term effectiveness (Ogunniyi et al., 2022).

The methodological approach combining parental perceptions with anthropometric measurements provides both strengths and limitations. While capturing lived experiences, the perceptual measures may lack the precision of validated scales like the Household Food Insecurity Experience Scale (FIES) now recommended by FAO (2022). The small anthropometric sample, while revealing clear patterns, limits statistical generalization. Future research in this context would benefit from larger, longitudinal designs that can track seasonal variations in food security and their nutritional impacts, particularly important in agricultural communities like Asari Toru (Uchendu & Abolarin, 2023).

These findings arrive at a critical juncture for Nigerian food and nutrition policy. The recently launched National Food Safety and Quality Bill (2022) and the National Multisectoral Plan of Action for Food and Nutrition (2021-2025) provide frameworks for integrated action. However, successful implementation requires context-specific strategies that address the particular challenges of the Niger Delta region, including environmental contamination, disrupted livelihoods, and infrastructure deficits (Nwosu et al., 2022). The threshold effect identified suggests that social protection programs should prioritize households at the cusp of moderate food insecurity to prevent irreversible growth faltering in children.

4. Conclusion

This study provides compelling evidence that household food insecurity in Asari Toru Local Government Area is a critical determinant of poor nutritional outcomes among children aged 4–8 years. The data illustrate a clear gradient: as household food security deteriorates, child dietary diversity declines, and risks of stunting and underweight increase significantly. The findings highlight a troubling nutritional threshold—once households fall into moderate or severe food insecurity, child growth impairment becomes prevalent, indicating that food access and dietary quality are

compromised beyond a point of resilience. The strong association between food security and socio-economic factors—including maternal education, household income, family size, water and sanitation access, and location underscores that food insecurity is not merely a matter of food availability, but a manifestation of multidimensional poverty. The clustering of disadvantages in food-insecure households suggests that children in these settings experience intersectional vulnerabilities that exacerbate their nutritional risk. Page | 244

Furthermore, the community's identification of preferred interventions—such as community gardens, nutrition education, and food subsidies—reflects a practical understanding of local needs and potential pathways to improvement. These findings collectively affirm that improving child nutrition in this region requires addressing the underlying socio-economic and environmental constraints that perpetuate household food insecurity.

The study contributes to the growing evidence base on the local manifestations of food insecurity in Nigeria's diverse regions. It underscores that achieving food security and improved nutrition for children requires moving beyond aggregate food availability to address the complex interplay of economic access, dietary quality, care practices, and environmental health. As Nigeria strives toward Sustainable Development Goal 2 (Zero Hunger) amidst economic challenges and climate pressures, these findings highlight the urgent need for targeted, multisectoral interventions that address both the immediate symptoms and underlying determinants of child malnutrition in communities like Asari Toru.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made; that Government and community leaders should;

1. implement programs that enhance local agricultural production, improve food distribution networks, and promote sustainable farming practices. This can help ensure a steady supply of nutritious food.
2. develop community-based educational initiatives aimed at increasing awareness of nutrition and healthy eating practices. This should include information on affordable, locally available food options.
3. establish and expand social protection programs, such as food assistance and cash transfer schemes, to support low-income families and ensure that children have access to adequate nutrition.
4. partner with non-governmental organizations and international agencies to leverage resources and expertise in addressing food insecurity and improving child nutrition.
5. implement robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks to assess the effectiveness of interventions aimed at reducing food insecurity and improving nutritional outcomes for children.

References

Adeyemi, O., Ogunniyi, A., & Olagunju, K. (2023). The nutrition transition in Nigeria: Evidence from household survey data. *Journal of Nutritional Science*, 12, e15.

- Akombi, B. J., Agho, K. E., Renzaho, A. M., & Hall, J. J. (2021). Trends in socioeconomic inequalities in child undernutrition: Evidence from Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (2003–2018). *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(19), 10156.
- Alaimo, K., Olson, C. M., & Frongillo, E. A. (2001). Food insufficiency and American school-aged children's cognitive, academic, and psychosocial development. *Pediatrics*, 108(1), 44-53.
- Amare, M., Arndt, C., & Abay, K. A. (2021). Urbanization and child nutritional outcomes. *The World Bank Economic Review*, 35(1), 223-248.
- Black, M. M., Victora, C. G., Walker, S. P., et al. (2013). Maternal and child undernutrition and overweight in low-income and middle-income countries. *The Lancet*, 382(9890), 427-451.
- Browne, N. T., Hodges, E. A., Small, L., Snethen, J. A., Frenn, M. D., & Irving, S. Y. (2021). Childhood obesity within the lens of racism. *Pediatric Obesity*, 16(5), e12752.
- Diouf, I., Quevenco, E., Idohou-Dossou, N., & Wade, S. (2021). The double burden of malnutrition in developing countries: A systematic review. *Current Developments in Nutrition*, 5(4), nzab018.
- FAO. (2021). The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2021. Retrieved from [FAO website](<http://www.fao.org/publications/sofi/2021/en/>)
- FAO. (2022). *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022: Repurposing food and agricultural policies to make healthy diets more affordable*. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Gelli, A., et al. (2016). The role of school feeding in improving food security and nutrition. *Food Security*, 8(4), 757-769.
- Global Panel on Agriculture and Food Systems for Nutrition. (2020). *Future food systems: For people, our planet, and prosperity*. <https://www.glopan.org/foresight2/>
- Gundersen, C., & Ziliak, J. P. (2015). Food insecurity and health outcomes. *Health Affairs*, 34(11), 1830-1839.
- Headey, D. D., & Alderman, H. H. (2019). The relative caloric prices of healthy and unhealthy foods differ systematically across income levels and continents. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 149(11), 2020-2033.
- Hendriks, S. L., Montgomery, H., Benton, T., Badiane, O., Castro de la Mata, G., Fanzo, J., & Zornetzer, H. (2022). Environmental and climate justice in food systems. In *Science and Innovations for Food Systems Transformation* (pp. 553-575). Springer, Cham.
- Nwosu, U. O., Ogbuabor, D. C., & Nwosu, E. O. (2022). Oil extraction, environmental degradation and food security in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 13(2), 290-306.

- Ogunniyi, A. I., Mavrotas, G., Olagunju, K. O., Fadare, O., & Adedoyin, R. (2022). Impact of COVID-19 on food security in Nigeria: The role of social protection policies. *Agricultural and Food Economics*, 10(1), 3.
- Owoo, N. S., & Lambon-Quayefio, M. P. (2021). The paradox of food security and welfare in Ghana. *Development Studies Research*, 8(1), 64-76.
- Oyeyinka, R. A., & Ajani, E. N. (2022). Rural-urban food system linkages and household food security in Nigeria. *Journal of Agribusiness in Developing and Emerging Economies*, 12(4), 633-650.
- Ruel, M. T. (2003). Operationalizing dietary diversity: A review of measurement issues and research priorities. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 133(11), 3911S-3926S.
- Uchendu, F. N., & Abolarin, T. O. (2023). Seasonal variations in household food security and child nutritional status in rural Nigeria. *Food Security*, 15(1), 203-215.
- UNICEF. (2021). The State of the World's Children 2021. Retrieved from [UNICEF website] (<https://www.unicef.org/reports/state-worlds-children-2021>)
- Victora, C. G., de Onis, M., Hallal, P. C., et al. (2010). Worldwide timing of growth faltering: revisiting implications for interventions. *Pediatrics*, 125(3), e473-e480.
- World Health Organization. (2020). Childhood overweight and obesity. Retrieved from [WHO website] (<https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/childhood-overweight-and-obesity>).

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